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“Genetic variability at the catalytic site of the SARS-CoV-2 RNA MTase NSP16 and the predicted effects of mutations on SAM and RNA binding”

Methods

The coronavirus genome size is large, about 30 kb single-stranded positive RNA. The RNA molecule is 5' capped and has 3'-poly-A tail. The viral RNA is the molecular template which is translated to make viral proteins. The products of the first open reading frame are polyprotein 1a and 1ab, which are further processed to make the non-structural proteins (NSPs). The assembly of the NSPs forms the replication translation complex (RTC), and among those NSPs, there are two enzymes involved in viral mRNA capping. The capping of the viral mRNA is a critical viral defense mechanism against the immune system. One of these two enzymes is NSP16, which is a SAM-dependent m7GpppA-specific 2'-O-methyltransferase (2'-O-MTase), which means that it uses the cofactor, S-adenosyl-L-methionine (SAM) as the methyl donor. (1) NSP16 forms a stable dimer with NSP10, then NSP10-NSP16 mediates 2'-O-methylation of coronavirus mRNA to prevent viral recognition by the host to avoid immune response during mRNA translation. (1, 2) This viral mechanism makes NSP16 protein an appealing target for anti-SARS-CoV-2 therapies.

In this report, I will walk you through the steps for finding the active site of SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase and its druggability analysis. Then, I will explain how we picked the surrounding residues that line the NSP16 catalytic pocket. In the end, I show the energy calculations corresponding to the variants from SARS-CoV-2 patient samples at the catalytic site of 2'-O-MTase. Alongside that, you will see a Table that shows all the possible mutations at the catalytic site of 2'-O-MTase and the predicted changes in endogenous ligand-binding due to those mutations.

I use NSP16 in this document to refer to SARS-CoV-2 SAM-dependent m7GpppA-specific 2'-O-methyltransferase.

Step 1: Identify the potential drug-binding sites on NSP16 (PDB: 6wvn).

The very first step was to identify the potential drug-binding sites on NSP16 (PDB: 6wvn). We used ICM PocketFinder (Molsoft, SD) to determine the pockets. The druggability analysis was done using SiteMap (Schrodinger, NY). The results are shown in Figure 1. The druggability score (Dscore) of the catalytic site of NSP16 is 0.98, which is indicative of a druggable site.

Figure 1. Druggability analysis of NSP16 catalytic site. The blue and red pocket show the catalytic site of the NSP16 molecule, where the blue pocket is occupied by SAM and the red pocket is occupied by a substrate RNA molecule.

Step 2: Determine the residues that line the catalytic site of NSP16.

Next, to determine the residues that line the catalytic site, we picked the sidechains of the protein facing towards the pocket within its 2.8 Å vicinity. At the end, we selected 39 residues that met these criteria. In figure 2 those residues are shown in sticks representation. Here is a full list of these 39 residues: K6822,C6823,D6824,L6825,Y6828,N6841,K6844,Y6845,H6867,F6868,G6869,A6870,G6871,S6872,P6878,G6879,S6896,D6897,L6898,N6899,D6912,C6913,D6928,M6929,Y6930,D6931,P6932,T6934,K6935,V6937,F6947,K6968,T6970,E6971,H6972,N6996,S6999,S7000,E7001.

Figure 2. The neighboring residues lining the catalytic pocket of NSP16.

Step 3: Make diversity dendrograms for the NSP16 catalytic site using the sequences of the entries of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera in UniProt database.

Using the sequences of Alpha and Betacoronavirus genera from UniProt, we put together a diversity dendrogram while focusing on the catalytic site of NSP16 catalytic site. There were 28 unique entries in UniProt for both Alpha- and Betacoronavirus that we aligned using multiple sequence alignment in ICM. The diversity dendrogram is shown in Figure 3. Figure 4 is the color-coded representation of NSP16 to highlight the non-conserved residues of the Alpha and Betacoronavirus genera based on the diversity dendrogram in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The diversity dendrogram of the catalytic site of 2'-O-MTase for the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera.

Figure 4. Color-coded representation of SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase (PDB: 6wvn). The green color shows the non-conserved residues among the UniProt entries from the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera. These residues include: K6822, C6823, D6824, F6868, G6871, S6872, S6896, L6898, N6899, D6912, M6929, P6932, T6934, K6935, V6937, H6972.

Next, we looked at the conservation of NSP16 catalytic site residues among the entries of the Betacoronavirus genus separately, as shown in the diversity dendrogram in Figure 5. I highlight the non-conserved residues of NSP16 catalytic site among Betacoronavirus entries in the color-coded representation of NSP16 in Figure 6.

Figure 5. The diversity dendrogram of NSP16 catalytic site residues among the UniProt entries of the Betacoronavirus genus.

Figure 6. Color-coded representation of SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase (PDB: 6wvn). The green color shows the non-conserved residues among the UniProt entries from the Betacoronavirus genus. These residues include: K6822, C6823, D6824, F6868, S6872, S6896, L6898, N6899, D6912, P6932, T6934, K6935, V6937, H6972.

Step 4: Genetic diversity at the catalytic site of 2'-O-MTase among SARS-CoV-2 samples

In our next step, we wanted to look at the genetic diversity of NSP16 among SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients. Like my previous analysis of the SARS-CoV-2 main protease catalytic site, I sent the 39 residues lining the catalytic site of NSP16 to Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from EBI. He then looked at more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples to find the variants at this site. Below in Table 1, you can see the six non-synonymous variants that Nicola has identified in his sample batch and the number of each variant at a specific sidechain. For example, at position Ser6896 of NSP16, 15873 SARS-CoV-2 samples have a serine (S) residue while one sample had a leucine (L) residue. Among these six positions, residue 6932 is more unstable than the others, with proline found in 15847 samples and serine in 26.

Non-synonymous variations at NSP16 catalytic site	
1)	Ser6896 S (15873), L (1)
2)	Leu6898 L (15873), F (1)
3)	Asp6912 D (15873), G (1)
4)	Pro6932 P (15847), S (26)
5)	Pro6932 P (15847), T (1)
6)	Ser7000 S (15843), F (1)

Table 1. The non-synonymous variants at NSP16 catalytic site.

Step 5: Predicting the effect of mutations from SARS-CoV-2 samples on the binding of endogenous ligands, the cofactor SAM and the RNA molecule, with NSP16.

Since there is no structure of NSP16 in complex with inhibitors, I evaluated the effect of these mutations on the co-crystallized endogenous ligands SAM and RNA. Chemical inhibitors should occupy the same site, and probably mimic several interactions made by endogenous ligands, which is why we use this structure as a first approximation. But two important things should be kept in mind here. 1-Mutations predicted to penalize SAM, or RNA binding, will not necessarily penalize the binding of future inhibitors (though they are more likely to). 2-The phosphate linker of RNA is highly flexible, and mutations at this site that are predicted to be penalizing may not be so.

To predict the effect of these mutations on the binding of SAM and the RNA molecule with NSP16, we used the ddGbind values calculated in ICM, as shown in Table 2. The color-coded structure in Figure 7 highlights the variants among the SARS-CoV-2 samples at the 2'-O-MTase catalytic site.

Residue	Residue Number	WT	Mutant	distance to SAM	distance to RNA	Ligand	ddGbind
a_6wvn.a/^S6896	6896	Ser	Leu	4.415	11.01	SAM	-1.1
a_6wvn.a/^L6898	6898	Leu	Phe	1.918	7.847	SAM	-0.2
a_6wvn.a/^D6912	6912	Asp	Gly	1.966	12.13	SAM	2.4
a_6wvn.a/^P6932	6932	Pro	Thr	3.064	2.586	RNA	-0.9
a_6wvn.a/^P6932	6932	Pro	Ser	3.064	2.586	RNA	-0.2
a_6wvn.a/^S7000	7000	Ser	Phe	11.74	1.768	RNA	56.2

Table 2. The energy calculations pertaining to the genetic variants of the SARS-CoV-2 samples at the 2'-O-MTase catalytic site. The ddGbind values are in Kcal/mol.

The mutations were predicted to have a minor effect on ligand binding ($-2\text{kcal/mol} < \text{ddGbind} < 2\text{kcal/mol}$) except for S7000F, which was very penalizing at 56,2 Kcal/mol and D6912G at 2.4Kcal/mol. Color-coded representation of SARS-CoV-2 NSP16 is shown in Figure 7, whereby we highlight the effect of mutations on endogenous ligand-binding (based on ddGbind values) using two colors. Orange color is used to show mutations that result in ddGbind values higher than 2.0Kcal/mol, and green refers to ddGbind values smaller than 2.0 Kcal/mol.

Figure 7. Color-coded representation of SARSCoV-2 2'-O-MTase (PDB: 6wvn). The colored areas on the mesh show the non-conserved residues across more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients. The orange-colored residue mutations, S7000F and D6912G, penalize ligand binding significantly and mildly respectively, while the green-colored residues mutations (S6896L, L6898F, P6932P, P6932S) do not penalize ligand binding significantly.

Likely, changing a serine residue to phenylalanine, which is a bigger amino acid would result in steric clashes in the RNA-binding pocket of 2'-O-MTase as shown in Figure 8. It would also lead to the loss of hydrogen bonds that were originally between the hydroxyl group of serine sidechain and the oxygen atoms of the triphosphates on the RNA molecule. However, it is notable that the phosphate linker of RNA is flexible and may potentially accommodate the mutation S7000F. In Figure 9, the 2-D diagram showing ligand interactions between some selected residue sidechains of the SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase and the RNA molecule is shown. D6912G is expected to disrupt the hydrogen bond between Asp and the amino (NH_2) on the adenosine ring of SAM cofactor. The ddGbind value of this mutation is 2.4 Kcal/mol which is mild but not negligible. The 2D-diagram showing the chemical interactions between SAM molecule and 2'-O-MTase are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8. Ser7000Phe variant at the SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase catalytic site (PDB: 6wvn). The channel occupied by the phosphate linker of the RNA molecule is occluded due to bulkiness of Phe (right panel) that replaced Ser7000 (left panel).

Figure 9. The 2-D diagram for ligand-interaction between SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase and the RNA molecule. The S7000 is labelled in an orange box. S7000 hydroxyl group makes hydrogen bonds with the oxygen atoms of the triphosphates on the RNA molecule. This diagram was made using PoseView in Proteins.Plus.

Based on our prediction, the rest of the non-synonymous mutations (S6896L, L6898F, P6932T, P6932S) from other SARS-CoV-2 variants do not penalize ligand binding significantly as they ranged between -1.5 to 1 Kcal/mol. (3) P6932 residue sidechains lie in proximity to the RNA and S6896, and L6898 are in proximity to the cofactor SAM-binding pocket of 2'-O-MTase.

Figure 10. The 2-D diagram for ligand-interaction between SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase and the SAM cofactor. The residues in orange box are the non-conserved residues from SARS-CoV-2 samples. This diagram was made using PoseView in Proteins.Plus.

Based on the expected effects of the mutations on ligand binding, it would be likely that a broad-spectrum inhibitor should bind to the sidechains of the regions in the ovals in figure 11. We exclude the S7000 sidechain as it is expected that the mutation S7000F from COVID-19 patients would substantially penalize ligand binding.

Figure 11. The mesh representation of SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase (PDB: 6wvn). The orange oval shows areas that broad-spectrum inhibitors should avoid. The green oval shows that broad-spectrum inhibitors should occupy. The oval excludes the orange area since based on the expected effects of the mutations of SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients, S7000F is expected to penalize RNA-binding significantly.

Step 6: Predict the effect of all possible mutations at the 39 sidechains of NSP16 catalytic site on SAM and RNA-binding.

Lastly, we assessed the effect of all possible mutations at the sidechains lining the catalytic site of NSP16 that would affect RNA or SAM-binding. Table 3 below shows all possible mutations and the ddGbind values corresponding to each. To determine the ligand that should be considered for ddGbind calculation, we used the distance function in ICM to measure which of the two ligands (RNA, SAM) is closer to each of the 39 sidechains lining NSP16 catalytic site. Based on that selection of the ligand, all possible mutations were modeled in ICM, and the change in Gibbs free energy in ligand binding was calculated and presented in Table 3. To see the script used in ICM, you can download `energy_matrix_NSPI6.icm` on this same Zenodo report.

It is likely that the residues of the rows with green color do not make optimal interactions with SAM or RNA substrate. This is reflected in the slight and non-significant lowering of ddGbind values of these residues (mutations are stabilizing) and hence the green color. Inhibitors could potentially make strong interactions (better than SAM or RNA) with wild-type sidechains at these positions. On the other hand, the sidechains whose mutations are shown in orange are likely the positions where 2'-O-MTase would better interact with SAM or RNA. As a result, the mutations of those sidechains are predicted to penalize SAM- and RNA-binding significantly and hence the orange color.

In the absence of structures in complex with inhibitors, the predicted effect of these mutations is on the binding of endogenous ligands. The effect could be different on the binding of future inhibitors, especially if inhibitors do not mimic receptor-ligand interactions observed with SAM or RNA.

INX	Residue	Ligand	Mutant Residue																			
			gly	ala	val	leu	ile	pro	cys	met	ser	thr	phe	tyr	trp	asn	gln	asp	glu	his	lys	arg
1	a_6wvvn.a/*K6822	RNA	-3.6	-3.8	-3.1	-2.7	-3.2	-3.7	-2.9	-3.4	-3.3	-2.1	0.7	-1.3	-2.0	-2.4	-2.0	-1.9	-1.3	0.0	-0.7	
2	a_6wvvn.a/*C6823	RNA	0.8	-0.3	0.1	1.9	0.2	-0.3	0.0	-0.2	0.2	-0.1	2.7	2.5	6.3	0.0	-0.1	3.4	4.4	-2.1	-1.5	0.2
3	a_6wvvn.a/*D6824	RNA	-1.2	-2.0	-1.4	-1.0	-1.6	71.0	-2.1	-1.3	-1.2	-0.8	-1.1	-0.9	-0.6	-0.5	-1.4	0.0	-1.2	-0.8	-1.0	-1.8
4	a_6wvvn.a/*L6825	RNA	2.7	2.3	-0.2	0.0	0.7	19.0	1.1	-0.7	3.0	3.5	3.7	3.8	0.3	-1.2	-0.1	4.8	2.5	-0.8	-2.7	-3.7
5	a_6wvvn.a/*V6828	RNA	17.8	15.0	13.7	19.1	19.8	14.3	17.6	131.7	17.3	13.8	6.8	0.0	7.8	16.0	20.9	17.3	17.2	10.1	63.4	106.5
6	a_6wvvn.a/*N6841	SAM	5.9	6.3	5.5	5.4	4.5	6.2	3.2	7.6	5.2	6.5	3.0	3.4	5.7	0.0	0.8	7.6	15.0	3.7	16.0	12.1
7	a_6wvvn.a/*K6844	RNA	-2.2	-1.5	0.3	3.1	1.1	-1.6	-0.5	2.6	-0.9	-0.6	-0.6	0.1	-0.3	-1.5	6.0	1.2	13.5	-0.9	0.0	0.0
8	a_6wvvn.a/*Y6845	SAM	5.3	5.6	6.6	7.5	6.4	6.0	6.6	5.6	6.4	6.4	4.6	0.0	6.0	7.7	6.4	9.1	9.0	5.2	-1.2	6.3
9	a_6wvvn.a/*H6867	SAM	2.3	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.8	56.3	1.8	1.9	2.0	1.9	-0.6	1.1	1.5	2.2	1.9	3.9	5.0	0.0	0.5	-5.5
10	a_6wvvn.a/*F6868	SAM	0.0	-0.3	-0.5	-0.2	-0.4	50.2	-0.5	-0.2	-0.3	-0.6	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.9	0.2	-0.2	2.4	-0.3	-0.4	1.9
11	a_6wvvn.a/*G6869	SAM	0.0	-1.0	-0.3	4.7	-1.3	76.8	-2.1	-2.1	-1.3	0.3	-2.0	-2.7	55.8	-1.2	-2.3	6.0	4.0	-1.0	-3.6	-4.7
12	a_6wvvn.a/*A6870	SAM	0.1	0.0	-0.5	0.4	-0.6	-0.2	-0.1	-0.5	0.6	-0.2	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.6	0.0	1.3	1.2	-0.2	-1.1	0.0
13	a_6wvvn.a/*G6871	SAM	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.3	-0.2	-1.3	0.0	-0.8	0.6	-0.3	-0.7	-0.5	-0.2	-0.7	-0.1	1.4	1.3	-0.3	-0.7	-0.6
14	a_6wvvn.a/*S6872	SAM	3.4	0.1	2.6	-0.2	12.1	52.9	-0.3	-0.6	0.0	-7.3	-0.2	-0.4	0.0	0.6	-3.3	2.0	3.3	-0.8	-2.1	-2.3
15	a_6wvvn.a/*H6878	SAM	6.3	5.7	5.3	5.7	5.1	0.0	4.8	3.8	7.7	5.5	4.2	3.8	4.5	4.8	4.7	7.4	5.9	4.5	5.3	5.4
16	a_6wvvn.a/*G6879	SAM	0.0	-4.1	-1.8	7.2	14.1	9.6	-3.3	88.9	-2.0	1.9	88.6	75.1	9.5	17.1	-1.0	2.3	-2.7	11.8	1.4	1.8
17	a_6wvvn.a/*S6896	SAM	-0.5	-0.6	-0.8	-1.1	-0.3	49.8	-0.1	-1.2	0.0	-0.6	-1.7	-1.5	14.8	0.3	-0.6	2.0	0.1	-1.0	-0.6	-0.8
18	a_6wvvn.a/*D6897	SAM	12.3	11.7	11.6	10.9	10.7	73.2	9.9	13.2	9.4	8.8	47.5	129.9	78.3	2.1	5.2	0.0	4.3	21.4	30.4	23.2
19	a_6wvvn.a/*L6898	SAM	3.5	0.7	3.1	0.0	4.9	7.6	1.0	0.4	0.5	3.3	-0.2	-0.5	0.5	0.6	-0.4	0.3	1.2	0.5	0.9	0.6
20	a_6wvvn.a/*N6899	SAM	-0.6	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.2	40.2	-0.1	-1.9	0.3	0.7	-0.3	-0.9	-0.9	0.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	-0.4	0.9	0.5
21	a_6wvvn.a/*D6912	SAM	2.4	1.2	0.5	0.5	0.6	2.2	0.6	0.8	0.5	1.0	2.7	2.9	4.5	-0.2	0.8	0.0	0.9	2.6	0.6	1.7
22	a_6wvvn.a/*C6913	SAM	3.2	1.2	-8.7	-5.0	-6.1	13.0	0.0	-1.1	3.1	1.1	-2.8	-2.2	138.3	2.6	-0.5	3.1	1.3	-6.0	-2.3	-1.0
23	a_6wvvn.a/*D6928	SAM	4.6	2.2	2.4	9.2	1.7	12.8	3.6	-3.7	5.6	2.8	20.0	20.6	61.8	10.2	7.3	0.0	-4.9	3.4	11.1	5.4
24	a_6wvvn.a/*M6929	SAM	4.1	3.2	2.0	-1.3	1.4	3.5	1.9	0.0	4.2	3.6	-2.0	-2.0	57.1	2.4	-0.2	7.0	6.4	-3.2	-1.1	-3.9
25	a_6wvvn.a/*Y6930	RNA	15.2	14.0	12.5	15.0	14.8	66.2	14.4	18.1	15.9	13.2	7.5	0.0	5.3	14.6	27.5	21.4	24.5	11.2	23.6	37.7
26	a_6wvvn.a/*D6931	SAM	0.4	1.0	0.8	0.7	1.2	1.0	0.6	1.4	0.4	1.3	0.9	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.4	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.8
27	a_6wvvn.a/*P6932	SAM	-0.3	-0.3	0.6	20.9	1.2	0.0	0.5	1.6	-0.2	-0.9	3.0	3.3	21.9	1.3	1.0	1.2	1.8	6.2	4.2	4.3
28	a_6wvvn.a/*T6934	RNA	0.7	0.6	0.1	1.3	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.7	0.6	0.0	1.2	1.0	0.6	0.3	0.2	3.4	4.3	0.7	-0.9	-1.3
29	a_6wvvn.a/*K6935	RNA	18.2	17.7	21.2	21.8	22.6	17.9	21.3	23.0	21.4	20.7	22.8	45.2	28.7	24.8	22.1	28.8	24.4	21.5	0.0	17.8
30	a_6wvvn.a/*V6937	RNA	0.7	0.3	0.0	1.9	4.0	-0.7	0.6	24.5	1.0	1.8	12.7	10.9	13.1	3.0	5.2	4.1	9.8	8.7	33.6	-7.8
31	a_6wvvn.a/*F6947	SAM	1.0	0.2	3.5	-0.8	4.3	0.6	-0.4	-1.2	-0.3	2.3	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.8	-2.5	-0.8	2.5	-0.1	3.2	-4.6
32	a_6wvvn.a/*K6968	RNA	1.9	3.7	6.6	6.0	5.7	2.3	6.4	5.9	3.7	4.8	7.4	12.9	11.2	3.6	11.5	13.1	23.8	5.4	0.0	2.6
33	a_6wvvn.a/*T6970	RNA	9.1	5.5	1.2	5.7	3.3	327.5	5.8	4.8	7.9	0.0	13.6	15.2	10.5	0.9	0.5	15.6	25.9	10.1	41.5	66.2
34	a_6wvvn.a/*E6971	RNA	-3.0	-4.9	-2.8	-4.8	11.3	-7.0	-4.1	-4.7	-5.0	-2.4	-5.0	-5.6	-4.7	-4.3	-2.0	-2.6	0.0	-4.3	-3.5	-0.6
35	a_6wvvn.a/*H6972	RNA	-2.7	0.0	0.5	5.1	7.1	37.8	0.6	94.1	0.4	1.0	-1.6	-2.0	7.0	-5.2	0.4	6.6	4.7	0.0	5.9	1.4
36	a_6wvvn.a/*N6996	RNA	-1.0	-0.7	-0.6	-2.6	-1.0	64.8	-0.4	-1.2	-0.1	-0.6	2.3	3.9	19.1	0.0	-1.2	4.1	1.7	-1.0	13.3	33.5
37	a_6wvvn.a/*S6999	RNA	3.3	0.6	3.0	13.1	4.3	53.0	7.6	18.6	0.0	4.1	47.2	30.3	36.0	10.8	22.6	18.8	24.0	34.2	37.7	114.4
38	a_6wvvn.a/*S7000	RNA	4.1	3.2	12.2	52.7	30.5	20.6	3.9	6.3	0.0	10.2	56.2	73.2	199.5	4.7	8.0	22.8	21.3	18.8	18.7	33.3
39	a_6wvvn.a/*E7001	RNA	-1.0	-1.4	8.4	-2.7	16.8	-2.0	-0.4	7.2	0.3	7.3	-1.4	-1.8	-1.0	0.8	-0.9	2.3	0.0	-0.5	1.2	0.8

Table 3. The energy matrix of mutations of the 39 residues lining the catalytic pocket of 2'-O-MTase of SARS-CoV-2. The energy unit is kcal/mol.

Table 3 color-coding based on ddGbind value (X) in Kcal/mol
X > 10.0
4.0 > X > 10.0
2.0 > X > 4.0
-2.0 > X > 2.0
-4.0 > X > -2.0
-10.0 > X > -4.0
-10.0 > X

Appendix:

We looked at the conservation of NSP16 catalytic site residues among the entries of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera, which you can find in the diversity dendrograms in figure 3 and 5. Following that, we used the energy calculations in table 3 to highlight sidechain positions at which the variants were predicted to penalize ligand-binding. Consider this example, at position S6872 of SARS-CoV-2 NSP16, we see that the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus entries can have both C and G (figure 3). Based on table 3, S6872G's ddGbind is 3.373 Kcal/mol, and S6872C's ddGbind is at -0.2776 Kcal/mol. Future pandemic coronaviruses may have a G at this position (the most penalizing mutation observed in past coronaviruses). We therefore assign a ddGbind of 3.4 at this position. Like this example, all the other residues went through the same analysis. We highlight the ddGbind values above 2.0 Kcal/mol in orange on the surface representations of NSP16 (figure 12). We applied a similar process to Betacoronavirus genus entries (figure 13). It is important to note that K6935L is predicted to affect RNA-binding significantly (ddGbind=21.2 Kcal/mol). This entry belongs to CVBQ (Bovine coronavirus) which has a rather questionable alignment with the rest of sequences where 2 sidechains are missing from this UniProt entry as shown below.

RVSLYNKYHLGAGSPGNDLYDCDMYD-LLI-KTEFNSSSE	CVBQ	Bovine coronavirus (BCoV) (BCV)
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Step 7: Map the genetic variations among the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus entries onto SARS-CoV-2 NSP16 crystal structure.

Figure 12. Color-coded representation of SARS-CoV-2 NSP16 (PDB: 6wvn). The green color shows the non-conserved residues among the UniProt entries from the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera that have ddGbind values between -2.0 and 2.0 Kcal/mol. The non-conserved sidechains highlighted in orange which are a total of four residues have ddGbind value greater than 2.0 Kcal/mol (S6872, L6898, K6935, V6837).

Step 7: Map the genetic variations among the Betacoronavirus entries onto SARS-CoV-2 NSP16 crystal structure.

Figure 13. Color-coded representation of SARS-CoV-2 2'-O-MTase (PDB: 6wvn). The green color shows the non-conserved residues among the UniProt entries from the Betacoronavirus genus that have ddGbind values between -2.0 and 2.0 Kcal/mol. The non-conserved sidechains highlighted in orange which are a total of three residues have ddGbind value greater than 2Kcal/mol (L6898, K6935, V6937).

References:

1. Rosas-Lemus, M. et al. The crystal structure of nsp10-nsp16 heterodimer from SARS-CoV-2 in complex with S-adenosylmethionine. bioRxiv 2020.04.17.047498; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.17.047498>. Apr 2020.
2. Hyde, J. L., and Diamond, M. S. (2015) Innate immune restriction and antagonism of viral RNA lacking 2-O methylation. *Virology* 479-480, 66–74. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2015.01.019>
3. Schapira, M., Totrov, M., Abagyan, R. Prediction of the Binding Energy for Small Molecules, Peptides and Proteins. *Journal of Molecular Recognition* 12(3), 177-90 (1999). [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1352\(199905/06\)12:3<177::AID-JMR451>3.0.CO;2-Z](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1352(199905/06)12:3<177::AID-JMR451>3.0.CO;2-Z)